

Colloidal doped semiconductor nanocrystals embedded in one-dimensional photonic crystals for ultrafast photonics

Ilka Kriegel¹, Francesco Scotognella^{2*}

¹ Functional Nanosystems, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Morego 30, 16163, Genova, Italy

² Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy

* Email : francesco.scotognella@polito.it

Abstract

The optical properties of strongly doped semiconductor nanocrystals depend strongly on the carrier density of the nanocrystals. These characteristics can be exploited for the design of innovative optical devices based on ultrafast switching potentially in the THz regime. In this study, the optical response of one-dimensional photonic crystals incorporating colloidal nanoparticles of a highly doped semiconductor such as indium tin oxide was investigated, taking into consideration the angular dependence of the photonic band gap and the position dependence of the photonic band gap on the light-induced tunability of the indium tin oxide doping.

Keywords: doped semiconductor nanocrystals; photonic crystals; ultrafast photonics.

Introduction

The topic of heavily doped semiconductors for ultrafast photonics is an emerging and promising area of research. This class of materials are particularly interesting for the infrared spectral window, as they are often compatible with microelectronic technologies, facilitating their integration into low-cost, mass-fabricated devices. In addition, their plasma frequency can be tuned chemically, optically or electrically over a wide spectral range [1–3]. Heavily doped conventional semiconductors such as Ge, Si, or III–V alloys play a crucial role in the field since they have successfully demonstrated unique optical properties and they are easily integrated on a silicon platform [4,5]. In addition to conventional semiconductors, manufactured mainly by top-down fabrication techniques, doped semiconductor nanocrystals, which have the special feature of being able to be fabricated in the chemical laboratory by chemical synthesis at mild temperatures, are gaining ground for ultrafast photonics [6–9]. Among these materials, there are many reports on copper chalcogenides [10,11] and doped metal oxides [12–14]. The inclusion of heavily doped semiconductors in photonic crystals allows the ultrafast control of the photonic band gap, which depends upon the alternation of materials with different refractive indexes in one, two and three dimensions at length scale comparable with the wavelength of light [15–18], by tuning the plasma frequency of such doped semiconductors [14,19].

In this paper, the optical properties of one-dimensional photonic crystals that include heavily doped semiconductor nanocrystals have been discussed. More precisely, a multilayer in which layers of indium tin oxide nanocrystals, among the most widely employed heavily doped semiconductor nanostructures [20–22], are alternated with layers of titanium dioxide nanocrystals is studied from a light transmission point of view by employing the transfer matrix method. The angular response of the light transmission has been studied. Moreover, the modulation of the photonic band gap by

photodoping of indium tin oxide has been analyzed. In the simulations, the wavelength dependent refractive indexes of the materials included in the photonic crystals are carefully considered.

Methods

The simulations in this work have been performed by employing the transfer matrix method [23–26]. A multilayer of materials deposited on a substrate with refractive index n_s and in contact with air (with refractive index $n_0 = 1.000277 \cong 1$) on the other side. The transfer matrix for the k th layer is given by [26]

$$M_k = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k d_k\right) & -\frac{i}{p_k} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k d_k\right) \\ -ip_k \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k d_k\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k d_k\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

with $\phi_k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k d_k \cos\alpha_k$, being n_k the refractive index, d_k the thickness of the layer, and $\cos\alpha_k$ the angle of the light beam propagating through the layer with refractive index n_k , related to the angle of incidence of the light on the structure:

$$\cos\alpha_k = \left[1 - \frac{n_0^2 \sin^2 \vartheta_0}{n_k^2}\right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

For transverse electric (TE) wave $p_k = n_k \cos\alpha_k$, while for transverse magnetic (TM) wave $p_k = \frac{\cos\alpha_k}{n_k}$. The matrix product $M = M_1 \cdot M_2 \cdot \dots \cdot M_k \cdot \dots \cdot M_s = \begin{bmatrix} m_{11} & m_{12} \\ m_{21} & m_{22} \end{bmatrix}$ gives the matrix of the multilayer made of s layers. We can write the transmission coefficient as

$$t = \frac{2p_0}{(m_{11} + m_{12} p_s) p_0 + (m_{21} + m_{22} p_s)} \quad (3)$$

For transverse electric (TE) wave $p_0 = n_0 \cos\alpha_0$ and $p_s = n_s \left[1 - \frac{n_0^2 \sin^2 \vartheta_0}{n_s^2}\right]^{1/2}$, while for transverse

magnetic (TM) wave $p_0 = \frac{\cos\alpha_0}{n_0}$ and $p_s = \frac{\left[1 - \frac{n_0^2 \sin^2 \vartheta_0}{n_s^2}\right]^{1/2}}{n_s}$. Finally, to calculate the light transmission of the multilayer photonic crystal we can use the following equation:

$$T = \frac{n_0}{n_s} |t|^2. \quad (4)$$

The wavelength dependent refractive index of titanium dioxide is taken from Ref. [27]

$$n_{TiO_2}(\lambda) = \left(4.99 + \frac{1}{96.6\lambda^{1.1}} + \frac{1}{4.60\lambda^{1.95}}\right)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

In the equations 5 λ is in micrometers.

The Drude model is employed herein to simulate the optical response of indium tin oxide [28,29]. Within the model, the frequency dependent complex dielectric function of ITO and FICO can be written as:

$$\varepsilon_{FICO}(\omega) = \varepsilon_1(\omega) + i\varepsilon_2(\omega) \quad (6)$$

Where

$$\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_\infty - \frac{\omega_p^2}{(\omega^2 - \Gamma^2)} \quad (7)$$

And

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{\omega_p^2 \Gamma}{\omega(\omega^2 - \Gamma^2)} \quad (8)$$

With

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{Ne^2}{\varepsilon_0 m^*}} \quad (9)$$

For ITO $N = 2.49 \times 10^{26} m^{-3}$, $\varepsilon_\infty = 4$, $m^* = 0.4m_e$ and $\Gamma = 0.1132 eV$ [7].

Results and Discussion

In this work, the optical properties of a one-dimensional multilayer photonic crystal made of indium tin oxide nanoparticle layers and titanium dioxide layers have been studied. For sake of clarity, such photonic crystals can be fabricated via spin coating deposition starting from colloidal dispersions of nanoparticles, functionalized with organic ligands, as exhaustively described in several publications [19,30–32]. A sketch of the fabrication procedure is reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scheme of the fabrication procedure a nanoparticle-based multilayer one-dimensional photonic crystal via spin coating deposition.

In Figure 2 we show the light transmission of a 6-bilayer indium tin oxide / titanium dioxide photonic crystal as a function of the angle of incidence of light. The thickness of the layers of indium tin oxide layers is 65 nm and the filling factor of the nanoparticles in the layers is 0.6. The thickness of the titanium dioxide layers is 75 nm, and the filling factor of the nanoparticles in the layer is 0.6. The plot at the top of Figure 1 relates to the TE polarization of light, while the plot at the bottom of Figure 1 relates to the TM polarization of light. For the TM polarization, the Brewster angle is evident at wider angles.

Figure 2. Transmission spectrum at different angles for a 6-bilayer indium tin oxide / titanium dioxide photonic crystal (top: TE modes; bottom: TM modes).

It is remarkable that the Fermi gas of the heavily doped semiconductor indium tin oxide is at the bottom of the conduction. Upon a photoexcitation of the an indium tin oxide-based photonic crystal with laser pulses in which the photon energy is above the electronic band gap of indium tin oxide (about 4 eV [19]), the number of carrier in the Fermi gas increases. Such photodoping results in a change of the plasma frequency (Equation 9). The change of the plasma frequency leads to a

variation of the indium tin oxide dielectric function (Equation 6-8), leading to a change of the photonic band gap [33].

Figure 2. (top) Transmission and differential transmission spectra of a 4-bilayer titanium dioxide / indium tin oxide photonic crystal upon inter-band photoexcitation, which leads to a carrier density change from $2.49 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ (black solid curve) to $8.49 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ (red dashed dotted curve); (bottom) Differential transmission with $\Delta T/T = (T_{doped} - T_{undoped})/T_{undoped}$.

In Figure 3 (top) the simulation of the photodoping for a 4-bilayer titanium dioxide / indium tin oxide one-dimensional photonic crystal is shown. In such simulation, the carrier density is changed from $2.49 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ (black solid curve) to $8.49 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ (red dashed dotted curve). The thickness of titanium dioxide layers is 73.5 nm, and the layers are without pores (unitary filling factor). The thickness of indium tin oxide layers is 112.7 nm, and the filling factor is 0.65. To highlight the differences between the undoped photonic crystal and the doped photonic crystal, at the bottom of Figure 3 the differential transmission, related to $\Delta T/T = (T_{doped} - T_{undoped})/T_{undoped}$, is shown. The differential transmission underlines the shift of the photonic band gap to photodoping. Such shift of the photonic band gap, together with the lateral fringes of the photonic band gap, lasts for one to few picoseconds being related to the electron-phonon scattering of the system [19].

Conclusion

In this work, the optical response of one-dimensional photonic crystals that include indium tin oxide nanocrystals, i.e., one of the most widely studied heavily doped semiconductor nanostructures, has been studied by employing the transfer matrix method and carefully considering the wavelength dependent refractive indexes of the materials. The angular response, for different polarizations, of the photonic crystals have been studied. Moreover, the simulation of the photodoping of indium tin oxide, which affects the position of the photonic band gap of the photonic crystal, has been pursued. Such study can be interesting for the engineering of ultrafast devices based on plasmonic materials.

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